

EXPANDING THE BASIS FOR THE FORMATION OF LOCAL REGULATIONS: AN ANALYSIS OF CITIZEN LAWSUIT DECISIONS

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Abstract

District court decisions related to citizen lawsuits have different characteristics from general district court decisions, because court decisions in this lawsuit have rulings ordering local governments to form laws. This research aims to analyse the legal position of district court verdict orders in citizen lawsuits to form regional legal products and to analyse and find a correlation between district court verdict orders in citizen lawsuits with the basis for the formation of regional regulations stipulated in Article 14 of the UUP3U and Article 236 of the Local Government Law. This research is a normative research by conducting a statutory approach, a case approach and a conceptual approach. the district court's decision on a citizen lawsuit that orders the formation of local regulations is final and binding and takes the form of condemnatoir in the form of punishing the local government. The correlation between the district court's decision and the provisions of Article 14 of the UUP3U and Article 236 of the Local Government Law must be done with a three-pattern approach, the first is to formally change the UUP3U and the Local Government Law, the second is to make efforts to review the UUP3U and the Local Government Law to the Constitutional Court and the last is to include the consideration of the district court's decision in the basis of 'weighing' local regulations.

Keywords: *Local Regulation; Judgement; Citizen Lawsuit.*

1. Introduction

This paper aims to describe another dimension in the formation of regional legal products that originate from court decision mandates. At first glance, this narrative may seem highly unconventional in our legal formation process, as the formation of regional legal products has thus far been guided by the provisions of statutory regulations. From the outset, this paper acknowledges that its analysis will not focus solely on a single object, but will instead examine

several aspects particularly concerning court decisions in citizen lawsuit cases. Citizen lawsuits, or suits brought by citizens, are not a new phenomenon in our judicial system; many cases involving such suits have been resolved by district courts. In addition, numerous papers and studies have addressed the subject of citizen lawsuits. However, not many have linked court decisions related to citizen lawsuits to the formation of regional legal products particularly regional regulations making this a compelling subject for deeper analysis. Whether recognized or not, court decisions constitute a rich source of legal information; yet their existence tends to be placed merely as secondary material in most research.

A citizen lawsuit is a suit filed by citizens in response to environmental pollution events. In practice, such suits are submitted to the District Court, specifically in the civil chamber.¹ Civil suits or cases brought before the District Court commonly involve unlawful acts (*perbuatan melawan hukum*), where the object of the claim and the resulting decision concern only the parties involved in the dispute. However, this condition does not apply to citizen lawsuits, as such suits are filed for the purpose of assessing unlawful acts committed by the government as a result of its failure to carry out its functions and authority, which has led to pollution and damage to the environment.

It is commonly understood that the standing of a district court decision differs from that of a Constitutional Court (*Mahkamah Konstitusi*/MK) decision. A district court decision limits the scope of its ruling (*amar putusan*) to the subject matter of the case concerning the unlawful or illegal act, whereas a Constitutional Court decision is *erga omnes* in nature and may order the formation of new legal norms. The *erga omnes* character of Constitutional Court decisions stems from the fact that such decisions are binding not only upon the petitioners, but also upon every Indonesian citizen. The principle of *erga omnes* is reflected in the provision stating that Constitutional Court decisions can be directly implemented without requiring any further decision from a competent official, unless otherwise stipulated by statutory regulations. This provision reflects the binding legal force of such decisions, and by virtue of their public legal nature, they apply to everyone not merely to the parties involved in the case.² This is constitutionally justified given the existence of the Constitutional Court as an institution that reviews laws against the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia (*UUD NRI Tahun 1945*). If the substance of the decisions issued by these two judicial institutions differs, an interesting question arises: can a decision of a district court civil chamber serve as a basis for forming law (regional regulation)?

In general, the formation of regional regulations within Indonesia's legal system as has been applied at both the central and regional levels is subject to the provisions of Law Number 12 of 2011 on the Formation of Statutory Regulations, as amended by Law Number 13 of 2022 on the Second Amendment to Law Number 12 of 2011 (*UUP3U*). Specifically, the formation of regional legal products is subject not only to *UUP3U* but also to Law Number 23 of 2014 on Regional Government (*UU Pemda*). These two laws serve as the legal basis for regional governments to form regional regulations. Both laws have established the foundations for enacting regional regulations, as affirmed in the provisions of Article 14 of *UUP3U* and Article 236 of *UU Pemda*. Neither of these provisions mentions that the formation of regional regulations may be carried out on the basis of a district court decision. At this point, there appears to be no fundamental problem, as the laws have set out these foundations very explicitly. However, in practice, district courts examining citizen lawsuits have in fact issued

¹Thoha Ridlo, Muhammad, Daffa Alfandy, Azaria, Rahmadianingrum Ahmad Rayhan, "Rekonseptualisasi Model Citizen Lawsuit Dan Pengoptimalan Society 5.0 Sebagai Upaya Reformasi Penegakan Hukum Acara Perdata Di Indonesia," *Jurnal Restorasi Hukum* 7, no. 1 (2024).

² Fadzlan Budi and Sulisty Nugroho, "Sifat Keberlakuan Asas Erga Omnes Dan Implementasi Putusan Mahkamah Konstitusi," *Gorontalo Law Journal* 2, no. 2 (2019): 95–104.

several decisions ordering regional governments to form regional regulations. Such events have occurred at the District Court of Balikpapan City and also at the District Court of Central Jakarta.

Before elaborating further on the substance of this research, it is important to first present several prior studies that are relevant to this research, in order to assess the novelty of the work being conducted. The first study, conducted by Febriansyah Ramadhan et al., is titled "*Determining the Type of Legal Product in the Implementation of Supreme Court Decisions on Judicial Review (A Study of the Follow-Up to Supreme Court Decision 28 P/Hum/2018)*"³. This study aims to analyze the types of legal products in the implementation of Supreme Court decisions. It is a normative study employing statutory and conceptual approaches. The study concludes that there are inconsistencies between the body responsible for formation and the type of legal product in both the object under review and the implementation of the decision. The type of legal product that was reviewed falls under the category of primary legislation, drafted with the involvement of two powers (the Regional Legislative Council/DPRD and the Regent), whereas the follow-up employed a legal product classified as subordinate legislation, formed unilaterally by the Regent. The study also explains that the Regent's Regulation issued as a follow-up lacks legal validity, as the Regent does not have the authority to independently draft general and locality-based norms that have no juridical basis in national regulations (Laws, Government Regulations, or Ministerial of Home Affairs Regulations). The follow-up must use an equivalent legal product namely, a Regional Regulation which carries strong legitimacy by virtue of involving two powers that hold a direct mandate from the people. This study differs fundamentally from the research conducted by the present author, as it specifically addresses the type of legal product for the follow-up to a Supreme Court decision.

Second, a study conducted by Ferdinan Rifaldi Solissa et al., titled "*Citizen Lawsuit Claims in the Legal System in Indonesia*"⁴. This study aims to assess the standing of citizen lawsuits within Indonesia's legal system, using a normative juridical research method. The study concludes that the standing of citizen lawsuits in the Indonesian legal system refers to prior judicial decisions that have become jurisprudence. Furthermore, the study also finds that citizen lawsuits in the Indonesian legal system have not yet been regulated under statutory provisions concerning procedural rules. This study differs from the research conducted by the present author, as it focuses its analysis solely on the standing of citizen lawsuits, whereas the research conducted by the present author is directed toward examining court decisions concerning citizen lawsuits that have an impact on the formation of regional legal products.

Third, a study conducted by Rizki Jayuska & Ismail Marzuki, titled "*The Problematic of Regional Regulation Formation by the Regional Government of Central Kalimantan Province for the Period 2016–2021*"⁵. his study aims to determine the effectiveness of the Governor of Central Kalimantan for the period 2016–2021 in the formation of regional regulations; to identify the obstacles and constraints faced by the Governor of Central Kalimantan in the formation of regional regulations; and to determine the efforts made by the Governor of Central Kalimantan to overcome such obstacles and constraints, using a qualitative research method. The study concludes that regional governments and the Regional Legislative Council (DPRD)

³ Febriansyah Ramadhan and Ilham Dwi Rafiqi, "Penentuan Jenis Produk Hukum Dalam Pelaksanaan Putusan Mahkamah Agung Tentang Hak Uji Materil (Kajian Terhadap Tindak Lanjut Putusan Mahkamah Agung 28 P/Hum/2018," vol. 11, 2022.

⁴ Ferdinan Rifaldi Solissa, Hendrik Salmon, and Mahrita Aprilya Lakburlawal, "Gugatan Citizen Lawsuit Dalam Sistem Hukum Di Indonesia," *Study Review* 2 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.47268/palasrev.v2i1.13678>.

⁵ Rizki Jayuska and Ismail Marzuki, "Problematika Pembentukan Peraturan Daerah Oleh Pemerintah Daerah Provinsi Kalimantan Tengah Periode 2016-2021," *Pagaruyuang Law Journal* 4, no. 2 (2021), <https://jurnal.umsb.ac.id/index.php/pagaruyuang>.

must first harmonize draft regional regulations (*Raperda*) with other statutory regulations whether of a higher or equivalent standing and must avoid provisions or subject matter that are presumed to be detrimental to the public interest. This study differs from the research conducted by the present author, as it focuses its analysis on the scope of problems surrounding the formation of regional regulations and does not link them to the existence of district court decisions.

Fourth, a study conducted by Hamzah et al., titled "*The Urgency of Regional Regulation Formation in the Administration of Regional Government: A Study in Makassar City*"⁶. This study aims to analyze the urgency of regional regulation formation in the administration of regional government in Makassar City, using a data collection method obtained directly from its sources in the field, which constitutes raw data gathered through interviews. The study concludes that the formation of regional regulations in the administration of regional government represents a manifestation of the authority granted to regional governments in the context of implementing regional autonomy and the task of assistance (*tugas pembantuan*), as well as accommodating the specific conditions of a region or further elaborating upon higher-level statutory regulations. This study differs from the research conducted by the present author, as the analysis carried out focuses on the formation of regional regulations that is grounded in statutory regulations, without connecting it to the existence of court decisions as a potential basis for regional regulation formation.

Drawing from the four studies outlined above, it is evident that there are highly significant differences between those four studies and the research conducted by the present author. Therefore, the research conducted by the present author carries novelty value. This research focuses on analyzing the existence of district court decisions on citizen lawsuits in relation to the formation of regional legal products. As previously described, the formation of regional regulations is ordinarily subject to the provisions of *UUP3U* and *UU Pemda*; however, with the existence of district court decisions on citizen lawsuits several of which order the formation of new law a new dynamic has emerged. Consequently, this situation gives rise to two fundamental questions: first, what is the legal standing of the order contained in a district court decision in a citizen lawsuit that mandates the formation of a regional legal product? Second, what is the correlation between a district court decision and the provisions of Article 14 of *UUP3U* and Article 236 of *UU Pemda* in the formation of regional regulations?

This research aims to analyze the legal standing of district court decision orders in citizen lawsuits for the purpose of forming regional legal products, as well as to analyze and identify the correlation between the orders contained in district court decisions in citizen lawsuits and the basis for the formation of regional regulations as regulated under Article 14 of *UUP3U* and Article 236 of *UU Pemda*. It is hoped that this research can serve as input for legislators namely the Regional Representatives Council (*Dewan Perwakilan Daerah*) and the President in conducting harmonization and synchronization of Article 14 of *UUP3U* and Article 236 of *UU Pemda*, as well as providing strong argumentative input and a solid foundation for regional governments in following up on district court decisions in citizen lawsuits for the purpose of forming regional regulations. In addition, this research may also serve as a reference for academics conducting further research, and for students, this research is expected to serve as a reference in final academic writing. The structure of this research is organized as follows: first, the introduction; second, the research methodology; third, the discussion; and finally, the conclusion.

⁶ La Ode Husen and Askari Razak, "Urgensi Pembentukan Peraturan Daerah Dalam Penyelenggaraan Pemerintahan Daerah: Studi Di Kota Makassar," *Journal of Lex Generalis (JLS)* 3, no. 8 (2022).

2. Research Methodology

The determination of a research method is an important matter in any study. This research is a normative study that allocates a portion of its analysis to district court decisions and statutory regulations particularly Law Number 12 of 2011 on the Formation of Statutory Regulations, as amended by Law Number 13 of 2022 on the Second Amendment to Law Number 12 of 2011 (*UUP3U*). Specifically, the formation of regional legal products is subject not only to *UUP3U* but also to Law Number 23 of 2014 on Regional Government (*UU Pemda*), both of which serve as primary legal materials. This research positions court decisions as primary data rather than secondary data, and therefore also employs the method of sociological jurisprudence as part of its analysis. Meanwhile, secondary legal materials encompass relevant literature books, papers, and scientific journals related to the scope of the analysis. The approaches used in this research are the statutory approach, the case approach, and the conceptual approach. This research employs descriptive analysis and content analysis techniques to analyze legal materials. Descriptive analysis is an analytical method that aims to describe, analyze, and summarize various conditions or situations found within the collected data. Meanwhile, content analysis is an analytical approach applied to legal documents, particularly statutory regulations..

3. Discussion

3.1. Legal Position of District Court Orders in Citizen Lawsuit Claims

Before elaborating further on the legal standing of district court decisions in citizen lawsuits with respect to the order to form regional legal products, it is first important to explain the concept of citizen lawsuits themselves. A citizen lawsuit, also known as a citizen's suit, represents a form of access for individuals or private persons as citizens to assess governmental actions relating to the public interest. The citizen lawsuit itself is actually a practice recognized and developed within the legal systems of common law countries. The form of citizen suits against state administrators concerning public interest rights known as citizen lawsuits is in fact not yet recognized within the civil law system in Indonesia. The citizen lawsuit emerged in countries adhering to the common law system, such as the United States.⁷ Beyond the United States, this lawsuit mechanism is also recognized in England, Australia, and Canada, all of which adhere to the common law system. At its core, it constitutes a citizen's suit against the accountability of state administrators (the Government or the State) for their negligence in committing unlawful acts (*perbuatan melawan hukum/PMH*) by failing to fulfill citizens' rights in ways that are detrimental to the public interest.⁸ With the remarkably rapid development of the legal system in the modern era, the citizen lawsuit is now recognized within the legal and judicial systems of Indonesia. The existence of citizen lawsuits has been acknowledged in Indonesia since the issuance of Central Jakarta District Court Decision Number 28/PDT.G/2003/PN.JKT.PST, filed by Munir et al. concerning the abandonment of Indonesian migrant workers in Nunukan.

⁷ Listyalaras Nurmedina, "Perbandingan Penyelesaian Sengketa Lingkungan Hidup Melalui Mekanisme Gugatan Warga Negara (Citizen Lawsuit) Di Indonesia Dan Amerika Serikat," *Simbur Cahaya* 28, no. 2 (December 31, 2021): 245, <https://doi.org/10.28946/sc.v28i2.1236>.

⁸ Bahrul Efendi, Achmad, Hariri2 Ahmad, "Analisis Yuridis Gugatan Citizen Lawsuit Dalam Konflik Lingkungan Waduk Sepat (Studi Putusan Pengadilan Negeri Surabaya No. 200/Pdt.G/2019/Pn. Sby Jo No. 544/Pdt/2020/Pt)," *RES JUDICATA* 5, no. 2 (2022): 110–20.

Every district court decision is, in principle, final and binding — although legal remedies are provided for under the law, ultimately the decision will revert to its final and binding nature as well. A court decision represents the crown of the judicial institution and carries a very strong command value to be implemented. It is this very quality that gives rise to the notion that failure to implement a court decision constitutes an act of defiance and denial against the ruling. A judge who decides a case is a figure assumed to possess a mature disposition and broad perspective, making it highly constructive if they are willing to consider as many deliberations as possible before rendering a decision. This means that arguments for rejecting the examination of decisions that have not yet obtained permanent legal force become irrelevant as long as the analysis is conducted by competent parties who are far removed from any conflict of interest.⁹

Likewise, district court decisions in citizen lawsuits carry a final and binding nature upon the defendant. One measurable and assessable indicator of the level of compliance of regulation-makers with court decisions can be seen from how such regulation-makers follow up on the relevant decision. Each operative part of a decision (*amar putusan*) carries different consequences particularly for regulation-makers. In the case of a decision ordering implementation, the administrative body or official responsible for forming regulations is obligated to implement and follow up on such a decision.

Unlike district court decisions in the civil chamber in general, decisions on citizen lawsuits are directed not toward individual interests but toward the public interest. As such, the focus of the lawsuit is public policy carried out by the government or regional government. Given that the scope of the lawsuit concerns public policy for the public interest, it is inevitable that district court decisions will order the government and regional governments to revise policies or form statutory regulations. The Balikpapan District Court Decision Number 99/Pdt.G/2019/PN Bpp, handed down on August 18, 2020, is a decision on a citizen lawsuit concerning an environmental pollution case involving an oil spill in Balikpapan Bay caused by the rupture of a pipeline belonging to PT. Pertamina Refinery Unit V. The oil spill resulted in the contamination of an affected area of up to 7,000 hectares, with an affected coastline on the side of Balikpapan City and North Penajam Paser Regency stretching up to 60 kilometers. One of the operative parts of this district court decision orders the regional government to enact a Regional Regulation on the Coastal Zone and Small Islands Zoning Plan (*Rencana Zonasi Wilayah Pesisir dan Pulau-Pulau Kecil/RZWP-3K*) for East Kalimantan Province.

In addition to the Balikpapan District Court decision above, there is also Central Jakarta District Court Decision Number 374/Pdt.G/LH/2019/PN.Jkt.Pst., relating to environmental pollution in Jakarta. The operative part of this court decision likewise orders the regional government to formulate and implement an "*Air Pollution Control Strategy and Action Plan*" by taking into account the distribution of emissions from pollution sources in a focused, targeted manner, and with the involvement of public participation. Furthermore, Palangka Raya District Court Decision Number 118/Pdt.G/LH/2016/PN.Plk., relates to a case concerning government negligence in issuing forestry and plantation permits that caused massive fires in

⁹ Shidarta Shidarta, "Putusan Pengadilan Sebagai Objek Penulisan Artikel Ilmiah," *Undang: Jurnal Hukum* 5, no. 1 (July 11, 2022): 105–42, <https://doi.org/10.22437/ujh.5.1.105-142>.

Central Kalimantan in 2015.¹⁰ One of the operative parts of this district court decision orders the regional government to issue seven implementing regulations derived from Law Number 32 of 2009 on Environmental Protection and Management, which are essential for the prevention and mitigation of forest and land fires, with the involvement of community participation.

One of the operative parts of this district court decision orders the regional government to issue seven implementing regulations derived from Law Number 32 of 2009 on Environmental Protection and Management, which are essential for the prevention and mitigation of forest and land fires, with the involvement of community participation. Examining the three district court decisions above, it is evident that there are orders directed at law-makers in this case, regional governments to enact regional regulations. Such decision orders are, in a legal context, obligatory for regional governments to follow up on. The nature of these district court decisions is condemnatoir in form, in that they penalize the Government by ordering it to take action specifically to issue policies and undertake law-forming measures.¹¹

Therefore, regional governments, on the basis of district court decisions concerning citizen lawsuits, bear a legal obligation to follow up on such decisions by forming regional regulations. The district court decisions ordering regional governments to form regional regulations give rise to new legal consequences. First, the formation of legal products at the regional level is not always based solely on the criteria established under Article 14 of *UUP3U* and Article 236 of *UU Pemda*. Second, there has been an indirect substantive change to the provisions of Article 14 of *UUP3U* and Article 236 of *UU Pemda* with respect to the criteria for the formation of regional regulations.

3.2. Correlation Between District Court Decisions and the Provisions of UUP3U and UU Pemda in the Formation of Regional Regulations.

In the preceding sub-section, an elaboration was provided on the legal standing of district court decisions in citizen lawsuits, which are final and binding in nature and must be implemented by regional governments. This sub-section will elaborate on the correlation between district court decisions containing an operative order to form regional regulations and the provisions of Article 14 of *UUP3U* and Article 236 of *UU Pemda*, which serve as the basis for the formation of regional regulations. It is commonly understood that the formation of regional regulations is subject to the criteria established in both laws mentioned above. In addition to the provisions of those two laws, there is also Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 80 of 2015, which likewise governs the basis for the formation of regional regulations. Regional regulations differ from laws in many respects, and one of those differences is that regional regulations can only be formed insofar as they fulfill the fundamental criteria for the

¹⁰ Wiene Wardhani, "Unsur Kesalahan Dalam Gugatan Perbuatan Melawan Hukum (Onrechmatige Daad) Pada Sengakta Lingkungan Hidup (Putusan Nomor 118/Pdt.G/LH/2016/PN.Plk)," *Jurnal Verstek* 8, no. 3 (2020): 460–69.

¹¹ Destri Tsurayya Istiqamah and Teten Tendiyanto, "Sifat Eksekutorial Putusan Gugatan Warga Negara (Citizen Lawsuit) Pada Sistem Peradilan Di Indonesia," *LITERASI HUKUM* 7, no. 1 (2023).

formation of regional regulations. The bases or criteria for the formation of regional regulations are illustrated in the table below:

Table 1. Basis for the Formation of Regional Regulations (Perda) and Their Substantive Content

UUP3U (Law on Lawmaking) – Article 14	Regional Government Law (UU Pemda) – Article 236	Minister of Home Affairs Regulation (Permendagri) – Article 17
1. In the context of implementing regional autonomy and co-administration tasks;	1. Implementation of Regional Autonomy and Co-administration Tasks;	1. Mandates from higher laws and regulations;
2. Accommodating specific regional conditions; and/or	2. Further elaboration of provisions in higher laws and regulations;	2. Regional development plans;
3. Further elaboration of higher laws and regulations.	3. In addition to the above, regional regulations may contain local content in accordance with prevailing laws and regulations.	3. Implementation of Regional Autonomy and co-administration tasks; and
		4. Aspirations of the local community.

Source: Compiled by the author based on the provisions of UUP3U, the Regional Government Law, and the Minister of Home Affairs Regulation.

Table 1 above illustrates that none of the bases for the formation of regional regulations and the subject matter content of regional regulations as governed by the provisions of *UUP3U*, *UU Pemda*, and *Permendagri* accommodate the formation of regional regulations on the basis of a district court decision order. This gives rise to a fundamental question: is the action of a regional government in implementing a district court decision to form a regional regulation consistent with statutory regulations? The answer to that question is certainly no, given that the provisions of *UUP3U*, *UU Pemda*, and *Permendagri* do not regulate the formation of regional regulations on the basis of a district court decision order. However, on the other hand, a court decision that has obtained permanent legal force (*kekuatan hukum tetap*) is obligatory for the regional government to follow up on conversely, failure to follow up on a court decision order constitutes a form of defiance against the court's ruling. Therefore, an inconsistency has arisen between the court decision and the substantive norms contained in Article 14 of *UUP3U*, Article 236 of *UU Pemda*, and Article 17 of *Permendagri*.

In response to this situation, three patterns may be applied in establishing the correlation of legality for the formation of regional regulations. The first pattern is to make a formally limited amendment to the provisions of Article 14 of *UUP3U*, Article 236 of *UU Pemda*, and Article 17 of *Permendagri* by inserting the phrase "on the order of a district court decision concerning a citizen lawsuit," so that the normative construction of those three articles is reformulated as follows:

Table 2. Changes in Norms of Article 14 (UUP3U), Article 236 (Regional Government Law), and Article 17 (Minister of Home Affairs Regulation)

Legal Instrument	Before Amendment	After Amendment
UUP3U (Law on Lawmaking) – Article 14	1. In the context of implementing regional autonomy and co-administration tasks; 2. Accommodating specific regional conditions; and/or 3. Further elaboration of higher laws and regulations.	1. In the context of implementing regional autonomy and co-administration tasks; 2. Accommodating specific regional conditions; 3. Further elaboration of higher laws and regulations; and/or 4. Orders arising from court decisions.
Regional Government Law (UU Pemda) – Article 236	1. Implementation of Regional Autonomy and Co-administration Tasks; 2. Further elaboration of provisions in higher laws and regulations; 3. In addition to the above, regional regulations may contain local content in accordance with prevailing laws and regulations.	1. Implementation of Regional Autonomy and Co-administration Tasks; 2. Further elaboration of provisions in higher laws and regulations; 3. In addition to the above, regional regulations may contain local content in accordance with prevailing laws and regulations; 4. Orders arising from court decisions.
Minister of Home Affairs Regulation (Permendagri) – Article 17	1. Mandates from higher laws and regulations; 2. Regional development plans; 3. Implementation of Regional Autonomy and co-administration tasks; and 4. Aspirations of the local community.	1. Mandates from higher laws and regulations; 2. Regional development plans; 3. Implementation of Regional Autonomy and co-administration tasks; 4. Aspirations of the local community; and 5. Orders arising from court decisions.

Source: Compiled by the author based on the provisions of UUP3U, the Regional Government Law, and the Minister of Home Affairs Regulation.

Table 2 above illustrates that, in terms of substance, the existence of Article 14 of *UUP3U*, Article 236 of *UU Pemda*, and Article 17 of *Permendagri* has undergone an expansion of meaning on the basis of district court decisions in citizen lawsuits. Therefore, formally speaking, it is ideally necessary for the substance within the provisions of those articles to be amended in order to align with district court decisions. District court decisions in citizen lawsuits do not, in principle, review norms in the way that Constitutional Court decisions do. However, despite not reviewing norms, the existence of such district court decisions orders the formation of regional legal products. This situation introduces a new pattern and paradigm in the formation of regional regulations.

Figure 1. New pattern and paradigm in the formation of regional regulations

Source: Compiled by the author by correlating court decisions with the provisions of laws and regulations.

Figure 1 illustrates the new pattern and paradigm in the formation of regional regulations, which has undergone an expansion. The basis for the formation of regional regulations is no longer limited to statutory regulations alone, but may also be grounded in district court decisions particularly with respect to regional regulations related to the environment. Furthermore, in addition to the pattern described above, there is a second pattern for synchronizing court decisions with the norms contained in Article 14 of *UUP3U*, Article 236 of *UU Pemd*a, and Article 17 of *Permendagri* namely, by submitting a judicial review of *UUP3U* and *UU Pemd*a to the Constitutional Court. This step may be taken in order to provide a new interpretation of the provisions of Article 14 of *UUP3U* and Article 236 of *UU Pemd*a, to the effect that in addition to the existing criteria contained in those articles the order to form a regional regulation may also be interpreted as being carried out on the basis of a district court decision. Judicial review of laws by the Constitutional Court is regarded as an effective step for introducing new meanings into a formulated legal norm, thereby resulting in a change in the interpretive meaning of the relevant article provisions within *UUP3U* and *UU Pemd*a with respect to the basis for the formation of regional regulations.

In addition to the first and second patterns as described above, there is a third pattern that may be applied in the formation of regional regulations in relation to court decision orders in citizen lawsuit cases. This pattern involves using the court decision as a basis for the "considering" clause (*dasar menimbang*) within the provisions of the regional regulation, by making reference to the district court decision. In this way, it becomes evident that the formation of such a regional regulation was carried out on the order of a district court decision. This pattern may be illustrated as follows:

Figure 2. Placement of the District Court Decision in the "Considering" Clause of a Regional Regulation

DRAFT
REGIONAL REGULATION OF PROVINCE
NUMBER OF YEAR
ON
.....

BY THE GRACE OF GOD ALMIGHTY

THE GOVERNOR OF,

Considering : a. hat the philosophical foundation be inserted here.....
b. That in order to implement the Decision of the Balikpapan District Court Number 99/Pdt.G/2019/PN Bpp handed down on 18 August 2020 concerning a citizen lawsuit, it is deemed important to form a regional regulation.....;

Figure 2 above illustrates the pattern of regional regulation formation that directly incorporates the considerations of a district court decision within the "Considering" clause of the regional regulation. This step should also, from a legal standpoint, be regarded as a legally valid method of forming regional regulations, as it gives effect to the order of a district court decision that carries binding legal force. This pattern is employed in order to provide legal certainty in the process of forming regional regulations, because if reference is made to the provisions of *UUP3U* and *UU Pemma*, this process of forming regional regulations would be regarded as inconsistent with statutory regulations. Legal certainty is one of the most important values in law, as it will have a direct impact on the protection of citizens' rights in relation to the public interest. The three patterns described above are, in principle, patterns that can be legally implemented in the form of synchronization measures between district court decisions and the provisions of statutory regulations in the formation of regional regulations.

4. Conclusion

The findings of this research conclude that district court decisions on citizen lawsuits that order the formation of regional regulations are final and binding in nature, and take the form of *condemnatoir* rulings penalizing the Government to implement protective policies concerning citizens' rights that are connected to public services. Furthermore, the correlation between district court decisions and the provisions of Article 14 of *UUP3U* and Article 236 of *UU Pemma* must be addressed through a three-pattern approach: the first is a formal amendment to *UUP3U* and *UU Pemma*; the second is to pursue judicial review of *UUP3U* and *UU Pemma* before the Constitutional Court; and the third is to incorporate the considerations of the district court decision order within the "Considering" clause of the regional regulation.

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